

drought years to prevent the spread of mealybug. ■

Operational research on the control of brown planthopper in boro paddy

S. Acharya Chaudhuri, subject matter specialist (plant protection), All India Coordinated Project on National Demonstrations; G. L. Ray, assistant director of agricultural extension; and A. B. Mukherjee, head, Agricultural Entomology Department, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswa Vidyalaya, West Bengal, India

The brown planthopper (BPH) has been endemic in boro paddy in Khanakul since 1974, and has now spread to other blocks of Hooghly district and into Midnapore district.

To find an effective chemical control measure for BPH, a field experiment was conducted in March-May 1979.

Hand compression sprayers, widely used in the area for BPH control, have not been very effective. Therefore, foot sprayers fitted with high jet lance and double delivery hose were tested in the plots of 15 local farmers. Lindane and other recommended insecticides were tried.

Foot sprayers were more effective both in placing insecticides in the affected zone of the paddy plants and in covering the area. Foot sprayers could cover about four times the area of hand compression sprayers.

Lindane at 2 ml/liter of water was effective in controlling BPH. ■

The FARMCOP suction sampler for hoppers and predators in flooded rice fields

F. O. Cariño, P. E. Kenmore, and V. A. Dyck, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Research in rice insect ecology has been hampered by the difficulty of obtaining accurate absolute estimates of pest and natural enemy populations. FARMCOP, a simple new sampling device, was developed to remedy the problem; the name was derived from the names of the

The FARMCOP suction sampler. IRRI, 1979.

Sampling with FARMCOP and enclosure in flooded rice field.

persons responsible for its construction.

FARMCOP consists basically of a light weight automobile vacuum cleaner,

two batteries, and a collecting container (see figure). A square wire-frame enclosure of transparent plastic is care-